

Derivation of an Infinite Product Representation for the Factorial (x!) Using Sum-and-Difference Symmetric Structures

Publisher: SungKun Kim

$$(2m)! = (1.5 - 0.5) \times (1.5 + 0.5) \times (3.5 - 0.5) \times (3.5 + 0.5) \\ \times \cdots \times (2m - 0.5 - 0.5) \times (2m - 0.5 + 0.5)$$

$$(2m)! = \prod_{k=1}^m \{(2k - 0.5)^2 - 0.25\}$$

$$\prod_{k=1}^m \{(2k - 0.5 + x)^2 - 0.25\} \\ = (1 + x) \times (2 + x) \times (3 + x) \times \cdots \times (2m + x)$$

$$F(x) = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{(2m)!}{(1 + x) \times (2 + x) \times (3 + x) \times \cdots \times (2m + x)} \\ \cdot (2m)^x$$

$$= \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\prod_{k=1}^m \{(2k - 0.5)^2 - 0.25\}}{\prod_{k=1}^m \{(2k - 0.5 + x)^2 - 0.25\}} \cdot (2m)^x$$

$$x! = \lim_{m \rightarrow \infty} \prod_{k=1}^m \frac{(2k - 0.5)^2 - 0.25}{(2k - 0.5 + x)^2 - 0.25} \cdot (2m)^x \quad (1)$$

This paper decomposes the even factorial $(2m)!$ into a product of sum-and-difference formulas, $\{(2k - 0.5)^2 - 0.25\}$, which are symmetric about the odd half-integer $2k-0.5$. Similarly, the sequence of consecutive terms in the denominator, ranging from $(1+x)$ to $(2m+x)$, is substituted with a product of $\{(2k - 0.5 + x)^2 - 0.25\}$,—sharing the same symmetric structure—to define the numerical ratio between the two structures. By incorporating the correction term $(2m)^x$, which ensures convergence in the limit as $m \rightarrow \infty$ based on Euler's infinite product definition, this study derives the infinite product expression (1) that arithmetically penetrates the internal symmetry of the factorial $(x!)$.